

C:\GCMSsolution\Data\Project1\01210124_C_GCMS\7.qgd

Similarity Search Result

<< Target >>

Line#:1 R.Time:1.715(Scan#:344) MassPeaks:202

RawMode:Averaged 1.710-1.720(343-345) BasePeak:45.05(2339590)

BG Mode:Calc. from Peak Group 1 - Event 1 Scan

Hit#:1 Entry:268 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:97 Formula:C2 H6 O CAS:64-17-5 MolWeight:46 RetIndex:0

CompName:Ethanol (CAS) Ethyl alcohol \$\$ EtOH \$\$ Tecsol \$\$ Jaysol \$\$ Alcohol \$\$ Algrain \$\$ Anhydrol \$\$ Jaysol S \$\$ Ethyl alc \$\$ Thanol \$\$ Ethyl hydrate \$\$ Methylcarbinol \$\$ Ethyl hydroxide \$\$ Alcohol anhydrous \$\$ Denatured ethanol \$\$ SD Alchol 23-hydrogen \$\$ Tecsol C \$\$ Alcare Hand Degermer \$\$ ETHANOL(ETHYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ ETHANOL (ETHYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ C2H5OH \$\$ Absolute ethanol \$\$ Cologne spirit \$\$ Fermentation alcohol \$\$ Grain alcohol \$\$ Molasses alcohol \$\$ Potato alcohol \$\$ Aethanol \$\$ Aethylalkohol \$\$ Alcohol, dehydrat

Hit#:2 Entry:267 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:97 Formula:C2 H6 O CAS:64-17-5 MolWeight:46 RetIndex:0

CompName:Ethanol (CAS) Ethyl alcohol \$\$ EtOH \$\$ Tecsol \$\$ Jaysol \$\$ Alcohol \$\$ Algrain \$\$ Anhydrol \$\$ Jaysol S \$\$ Ethyl alc \$\$ Thanol \$\$ Ethyl hydrate \$\$ Methylcarbinol \$\$ Ethyl hydroxide \$\$ Alcohol anhydrous \$\$ Denatured ethanol \$\$ SD Alchol 23-hydrogen \$\$ Tecsol C \$\$ Alcare Hand Degermer \$\$ ETHANOL(ETHYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ ETHANOL (ETHYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ C2H5OH \$\$ Absolute ethanol \$\$ Cologne spirit \$\$ Fermentation alcohol \$\$ Grain alcohol \$\$ Molasses alcohol \$\$ Potato alcohol \$\$ Aethanol \$\$ Aethylalkohol \$\$ Alcohol, dehydrat

Hit#:3 Entry:266 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:97 Formula:C2 H6 O CAS:64-17-5 MolWeight:46 RetIndex:0

CompName:Ethanol (CAS) Ethyl alcohol \$\$ EtOH \$\$ Tecsol \$\$ Jaysol \$\$ Alcohol \$\$ Algrain \$\$ Anhydrol \$\$ Jaysol S \$\$ Ethyl alc \$\$ Thanol \$\$ Ethyl hydrate \$\$ Methylcarbinol \$\$ Ethyl hydroxide \$\$ Alcohol anhydrous \$\$ Denatured ethanol \$\$ SD Alchol 23-hydrogen \$\$ Tecsol C \$\$ Alcare Hand Degermer \$\$ ETHANOL(ETHYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ ETHANOL (ETHYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ C2H5OH \$\$ Absolute ethanol \$\$ Cologne spirit \$\$ Fermentation alcohol \$\$ Grain alcohol \$\$ Molasses alcohol \$\$ Potato alcohol \$\$ Aethanol \$\$ Aethylalkohol \$\$ Alcohol, dehydrat

Hit#:4 Entry:265 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:97 Formula:C2 H6 O CAS:64-17-5 MolWeight:46 RetIndex:0

CompName:Ethanol (CAS) Ethyl alcohol \$\$ EtOH \$\$ Tecsol \$\$ Jaysol \$\$ Alcohol \$\$ Algrain \$\$ Anhydrol \$\$ Jaysol S \$\$ Ethyl alc \$\$ Thanol \$\$ Ethyl hydrate \$\$ Methylcarbinol \$\$ Ethyl hydroxide \$\$ Alcohol anhydrous \$\$ Denatured ethanol \$\$ SD Alchol 23-hydrogen \$\$ Tecsol C \$\$ Alcare Hand Degermer \$\$

Hit#:5 Entry:270 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:96 Formula:C2 H6 O CAS:64-17-5 MolWeight:46 RetIndex:0

CompName:Ethanol (CAS) Ethyl alcohol \$\$ EtOH \$\$ Tecsol \$\$ Jaysol \$\$ Alcohol \$\$ Algrain \$\$ Anhydrol \$\$ Jaysol S \$\$ Ethyl alc \$\$ Thanol \$\$ Ethyl hydrate \$\$ Methylcarbinol \$\$ Ethyl hydroxide \$\$ Alcohol anhydrous \$\$ Denatured ethanol \$\$ SD Alchol 23-hydrogen \$\$ Tecsol C \$\$ Alcare Hand Degermer \$\$ ETHANOL(ETHYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ ETHANOL (ETHYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ C2H5OH \$\$ Absolute ethanol \$\$ Cologne spirit \$\$ Fermentation alcohol \$\$ Grain alcohol \$\$ Molasses alcohol \$\$ Potato alcohol \$\$ Aethanol \$\$ Aethylalkohol \$\$ Alcohol, dehydrat

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Line#:2 R.Time:1.810(Scan#:363) MassPeaks:165
 RawMode:Averaged 1.805-1.815(362-364) BasePeak:42.05(181763)
 BG Mode:Calc. from Peak Group 1 - Event 1 Scan

Hit#:1 Entry:690 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:94 Formula:C3 H8 O CAS:71-23-8 MolWeight:60 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Propanol (CAS) Propanol \$\$ n-Propanol \$\$ n-Propyl alcohol \$\$ Optal \$\$ n-Propan-1-ol \$\$ Osmosol extra \$\$ Ethylcarbinol \$\$ Propyl alcohol \$\$ Propylic alcohol \$\$ 1-Propyl alcohololol \$\$ 1-Hydroxypropane \$\$ 1-PROPANOL(N-PROPYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ 1-PROPANOL (N-PROPYL ALCOHOL) \$\$ 1-Propyl alcohol \$\$ n-C3H7OH \$\$ Propanol-1 \$\$ Propan-1-ol \$\$ n-Propyl alcohol \$\$ Alcool propilico \$\$ Alcool propylique \$\$ Propanole \$\$ Propanolen \$\$ Propanoli \$\$ Propylowy alkohol \$\$ UN 1274 \$\$

Hit#:2 Entry:603 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:86 Formula:C3 H7 D O CAS:4712-36-1 MolWeight:60 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-PROPANOL-O-D \$\$

Hit#:3 Entry:666 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:85 Formula:C2 H8 N2 CAS:57-14-7 MolWeight:60 RetIndex:0

CompName:Hydrazine, 1,1-dimethyl- (CAS) N,N-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ UDMH \$\$ Dimazin \$\$ Dimazine \$\$ u-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ 1,1-Dimethyl hydrazine \$\$ unsym-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ Hydrazine, N,N-dimethyl- \$\$ Unsymmetrical dimethylhydrazine \$\$ as-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ (CH3)2NN H2 \$\$ Dimethylhydrazine,unsymmetrical \$\$ Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ Dimethylhydrazine, as \$\$ 1,1-Dimethylhydrazin \$\$ asymmetric Dimethylhydrazin e \$\$ uns-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ DMH \$\$ Niesymetryczna dwu metylohydrazyna \$\$ Rcr waste number U098 \$\$ UN 1163 \$\$ unsyMe

Hit#:4 Entry:668 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:85 Formula:C2 H8 N2 CAS:540-73-8 MolWeight:60 RetIndex:0

CompName:Hydrazine, 1,2-dimethyl- (CAS) sym-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ DMH \$\$ SDMh \$\$ Hydrazomethane \$\$ 1,2-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ N,N'-Di methylhydrazine \$\$ s-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ (CH3NH)2 \$\$ 1,2-Dimethylhydrazin \$\$ Dimethylhydrazine, symmetrical \$\$ Rcr waste number U099 \$\$ S Symetryczna dwumetylohydrazyna \$\$ UN 2382 \$\$

Hit#:5 Entry:665 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:85 Formula:C2 H8 N2 CAS:57-14-7 MolWeight:60 RetIndex:0

CompName:Hydrazine, 1,1-dimethyl- (CAS) N,N-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ UDMH \$\$ Dimazin \$\$ Dimazine \$\$ u-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ 1,1-Dimethyl hydrazine \$\$ unsym-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ Hydrazine, N,N-dimethyl- \$\$ Unsymmetrical dimethylhydrazine \$\$ as-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ (CH3)2NN H2 \$\$ Dimethylhydrazine,unsymmetrical \$\$ Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ Dimethylhydrazine, as \$\$ 1,1-Dimethylhydrazin \$\$ asymmetric Dimethylhydrazin e \$\$ uns-Dimethylhydrazine \$\$ DMH \$\$ Niesymetryczna dwu metylohydrazyna \$\$ Rcr waste number U098 \$\$ UN 1163 \$\$ unsyMe

<< Target >>

Line#:3 R.Time:1.930(Scan#:387) MassPeaks:210
 RawMode:Averaged 1.925-1.935(386-388) BasePeak:43.10(753757)
 BG Mode:Calc. from Peak Group 1 - Event 1 Scan

Hit#:1 Entry:1798 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:98 Formula:C4 H10 O CAS:78-83-1 MolWeight:74 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Propanol, 2-methyl- (CAS) Isobutyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ Isobutanol \$\$ Isopropylcarbinol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$

Hit#:2 Entry:1793 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:98 Formula:C4 H10 O CAS:78-83-1 MolWeight:74 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Propanol, 2-methyl- (CAS) Isobutyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ Isobutanol \$\$ Isopropylcarbinol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ 2-methylpropanol \$\$ 2-Methylpropan-1-ol \$\$ iso-C4H9OH \$\$ Fermentation butyl alcohol \$\$ 1-Hydroxymethylpropane \$\$ 2-Methylpropanol-1 \$\$ 2-Methylpropyl alcohol \$\$ Butanol-iso \$\$ Alcool isobutylique \$\$ Isobutylalkohol \$\$ Rera waste number U140 \$\$ UN 1212 \$\$ iso-butanol \$\$

Hit#:3 Entry:1789 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:98 Formula:C4 H10 O CAS:78-83-1 MolWeight:74 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Propanol, 2-methyl- (CAS) Isobutyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ Isobutanol \$\$ Isopropylcarbinol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ 2-methylpropanol \$\$ 2-Methylpropan-1-ol \$\$ iso-C4H9OH \$\$ Fermentation butyl alcohol \$\$ 1-Hydroxymethylpropane \$\$ 2-Methylpropanol-1 \$\$ 2-Methylpropyl alcohol \$\$ Butanol-iso \$\$ Alcool isobutylique \$\$ Isobutylalkohol \$\$ Rera waste number U140 \$\$ UN 1212 \$\$ iso-butanol \$\$

Hit#:4 Entry:1788 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:97 Formula:C4 H10 O CAS:78-83-1 MolWeight:74 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Propanol, 2-methyl- (CAS) Isobutyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ Isobutanol \$\$ Isopropylcarbinol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ 2-methylpropanol \$\$ 2-Methylpropan-1-ol \$\$ iso-C4H9OH \$\$ Fermentation butyl alcohol \$\$ 1-Hydroxymethylpropane \$\$ 2-Methylpropanol-1 \$\$ 2-Methylpropyl alcohol \$\$ Butanol-iso \$\$ Alcool isobutylique \$\$ Isobutylalkohol \$\$ Rera waste number U140 \$\$ UN 1212 \$\$ iso-butanol \$\$

Hit#:5 Entry:1797 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:97 Formula:C4 H10 O CAS:78-83-1 MolWeight:74 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Propanol, 2-methyl- (CAS) Isobutyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ Isobutanol \$\$ Isopropylcarbinol \$\$ 2-Methyl-1-propanol \$\$ 2-methylpropanol \$\$ 2-Methylpropan-1-ol \$\$ iso-C4H9OH \$\$ Fermentation butyl alcohol \$\$ 1-Hydroxymethylpropane \$\$ 2-Methylpropanol-1 \$\$ 2-Methylpropyl alcohol \$\$ Butanol-iso \$\$ Alcool isobutylique \$\$ Isobutylalkohol \$\$ Rera waste number U140 \$\$ UN 1212 \$\$ iso-butanol \$\$

<< Target >>

Line#:4 R.Time:2.280(Scan#:457) MassPeaks:201
 RawMode:Averaged 2.275-2.285(456-458) BasePeak:55.05(408230)
 BG Mode:Calc. from Peak Group 1 - Event 1 Scan

Hit#:1 Entry:4141 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:98 Formula:C5 H12 O CAS:123-51-3 MolWeight:88 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (impure) (CAS) 3-Methyl-1-butanol \$\$ Isopentanol \$\$ 3-Methylbutanol \$\$ Fusel oil \$\$ Isoamylol \$\$ Isoamyl alco
 hol \$\$ Isobutyl carbinol \$\$ Isopentyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-4-butanol \$\$ Fermentation amyl alcohol \$\$ iso-Amyl alcohol \$\$ 1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (CA
 S) Fermentation amylalcohol \$\$ iso- \$\$ 3-Methylbutan-1-ol \$\$ Alcool amilico \$\$ Alcool isoamylique \$\$ Amylowy alkohol \$\$ Fuseloeel \$\$ Huile de f
 usel \$\$ Iso-amylalkohol \$\$ 3-Metil-butanolo \$\$ Isoamyl alcohol, primary \$\$ UN 1105 \$\$

Hit#:2 Entry:4135 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:97 Formula:C5 H12 O CAS:123-51-3 MolWeight:88 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (impure) (CAS) 3-Methyl-1-butanol \$\$ Isopentanol \$\$ 3-Methylbutanol \$\$ Fusel oil \$\$ Isoamylol \$\$ Isoamyl alco
 hol \$\$ Isobutyl carbinol \$\$ Isopentyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-4-butanol \$\$ Fermentation amyl alcohol \$\$ iso- \$\$

Hit#:3 Entry:4138 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:97 Formula:C5 H12 O CAS:123-51-3 MolWeight:88 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (impure) (CAS) 3-Methyl-1-butanol \$\$ Isopentanol \$\$ 3-Methylbutanol \$\$ Fusel oil \$\$ Isoamylol \$\$ Isoamyl alco
 hol \$\$ Isobutyl carbinol \$\$ Isopentyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-4-butanol \$\$ Fermentation amyl alcohol \$\$ iso-Amyl alcohol \$\$ 1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (CA
 S) Fermentation amylalcohol \$\$ iso- \$\$ 3-Methylbutan-1-ol \$\$ Alcool amilico \$\$ Alcool isoamylique \$\$ Amylowy alkohol \$\$ Fuseloeel \$\$ Huile de f
 usel \$\$ Iso-amylalkohol \$\$ 3-Metil-butanolo \$\$ Isoamyl alcohol, primary \$\$ UN 1105 \$\$

Hit#:4 Entry:4140 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:96 Formula:C5 H12 O CAS:123-51-3 MolWeight:88 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (impure) (CAS) 3-Methyl-1-butanol \$\$ Isopentanol \$\$ 3-Methylbutanol \$\$ Fusel oil \$\$ Isoamylol \$\$ Isoamyl alco
 hol \$\$ Isobutyl carbinol \$\$ Isopentyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-4-butanol \$\$ Fermentation amyl alcohol \$\$ iso-Amyl alcohol \$\$ 1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (CA
 S) Fermentation amylalcohol \$\$ iso- \$\$ 3-Methylbutan-1-ol \$\$ Alcool amilico \$\$ Alcool isoamylique \$\$ Amylowy alkohol \$\$ Fuseloeel \$\$ Huile de f
 usel \$\$ Iso-amylalkohol \$\$ 3-Metil-butanolo \$\$ Isoamyl alcohol, primary \$\$ UN 1105 \$\$

Hit#:5 Entry:4145 Library:WILEY7.LIB

SI:95 Formula:C5 H12 O CAS:123-51-3 MolWeight:88 RetIndex:0

CompName:1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (impure) (CAS) 3-Methyl-1-butanol \$\$ Isopentanol \$\$ 3-Methylbutanol \$\$ Fusel oil \$\$ Isoamylol \$\$ Isoamyl alco
 hol \$\$ Isobutyl carbinol \$\$ Isopentyl alcohol \$\$ 2-Methyl-4-butanol \$\$ Fermentation amyl alcohol \$\$ iso-Amyl alcohol \$\$ 1-Butanol, 3-methyl- (CA
 S) Fermentation amylalcohol \$\$ iso- \$\$ 3-Methylbutan-1-ol \$\$ Alcool amilico \$\$ Alcool isoamylique \$\$ Amylowy alkohol \$\$ Fuseloeel \$\$ Huile de f
 usel \$\$ Iso-amylalkohol \$\$ 3-Metil-butanolo \$\$ Isoamyl alcohol, primary \$\$ UN 1105 \$\$

